

A conceptual model to integrate operations strategies into circular and sustainable global supply chains

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Abstract

Rapidly increasing environmental degradation means that society seeks to adapt its activities to sustainable environments that comply with global requirements and regulations. The need arises to investigate what operations strategies companies use to be productive and sustainable. Currently, there is no conceptual model that integrates environmental sustainability strategies and circular economy principles into the entire supply chain. Here a conceptual model, dubbed as the circular and sustainable-global supply chain, is proposed. To develop the conceptual proposal, a methodology consisting of the following phases was used: visualisation, analysis, conceptualisation, modelling, validation and proposal. According to the main literature review findings, the strategies of sustainable and circular operations most widely used by companies are defined. Then the proposed model integrates these strategies at all supply chain levels, which are analysed based on sustainability dimensions by identifying inputs, outputs, drivers, constraints and external factors. Finally, the model is validated in six companies in the bus manufacturing industry in terms of levels of compliance and feasibility of applying the model's elements.

Keywords: operations strategy; sustainability; supply chain; circular economy; conceptual model

1. Introduction

Increasing industrial development and the environmental impacts that it generates make society integrate new strategies into its activities that tend to care for the environment (Sutherland et al., 2020). In this context, industries seek to implement an operations strategy that allows them to increase the efficiency of their products in a sustainable environment (Jha et al., 2022). An operations strategy in the industrial environment means taking actions and allocating resources to achieve performance objectives, i.e. cost, quality, flexibility, speed and reliability (Slack & Lewis, 2023), increase competitiveness (Paiva, 2017) and reap the benefits of sustainability through innovation (Miranda et al., 2023), remanufacturing and product sharing, for example (Niu et al., 2024). Thus, developing an operations strategy involves making a set of decisions about the structure and infrastructure of operations (Zatta et al., 2021). So, it focuses on three closely related concepts: (i) operational skills; (ii) operational practices; (iii) resources (Hayes & Wheelwright, 1984). Operations strategies are established in decision areas, such as capacity, supply networks, process technology, development and organisation of operations processes (Slack & Lewis, 2023), and are evaluated on political, economic, environmental, social, legal and technological dimensions (Aldás et al., 2024).

Globality in the supply chain helps to overcome the problems of a local supply chain, e.g. low turnover, high inventory investments, lost sales due to stockouts of certain items and

surpluses of these same items in other locations (Ikeziri et al., 2023). This is why supply chains aim to broaden their scope in a globalised environment by considering all the actors involved in it (Hald & Spring, 2023) by, thus, creating global supply chains (Raj et al., 2024). This means that the companies with global presence strive to improve global supply chains in terms of environmental, social and economic performance (Koberg & Longoni, 2019) and, consequently, take advantage of the production practices offered by other more advanced organisations (Lotfi & Saghiri, 2018). Globality also boosts renewable energies use, which significantly improves environmental care and reduces the negative ecological footprint (Damak & Güngör, 2023). It is important to analyse all the elements involved in not only production processes, but also in purchasing from suppliers because, particularly in emerging economies, it is necessary to help other companies to know and adopt the right type of technology and/or technologies to be acquired and the systems that can help them to bridge the technological gap between industrial production and product commercialisation (Irfan et al., 2022). In the overall supply chain concept, the driving factors to be considered are political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental (Mishra et al., 2019). In this context, logistics plays a key role and involves principles, such as outbound logistics, reverse logistics, warehousing and data management (Zennaro et al. 2022).

Climate change, ecosystem degradation, environmental pollution, the emergence of new technologies, variable customer demand and unanticipated disruptions in their global supply chains make industries pursue environmental sustainability (Singh et al., 2024). In this way, sustainable development goals (SDGs) are pursued through sustainable supply chain management, especially SDG 12, which promotes responsible production and consumption (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2020). For sustainable supply chain management to be efficient, waste streams must be quantified, hotspots identified and when to apply circular economy principles based on reduce, reuse and recycle with economic prosperity needs to be known (Kumar et al., 2022). Progress made towards sustainable development could be accelerated by adopting progressive technologies and developing new green products. There are also integrated multistage green supply models in which remanufacturing and manufacturing are considered together. There are other trends that are gaining ground in terms of ecological strategies such as biomimicry, which links the circular economy with sustainability and environmental care.(Eid & Al-Abdallah, 2024) Most green supply chain models focus on manufacturing and remanufacturing, but do not take into account reconditioning activities where reverse logistics is used to collect used products and recondition them (Rani et al., 2022), similarly to Becerra et al. (2024) in a sustainable copper mining closed-loop supply chain. Accordingly, companies should standardise their processes from a sustainability perspective (Castka, 2020) by addressing its three dimensions: economic, environmental and social (Fathi et al., 2024).

In 2002, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation globally promoted circular economy by highlighting its potential for efficient and sustainable resource management. Later, according to (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013), the European Union and China began to incorporate circular economy into their sustainable development policies (Bundgaard & Huulgaard, 2019a). Circular economy principles are more frequently adopted by companies as an enabler towards sustainability from an environmental point of view, and also as an alternative to the dominant linear economic model (Muhammad Farooque et al. 2022). Hence circular supply chain management is born, which is positively related to financial performance: Thus, for example, investment in low-carbon assets allows for a better climate commitment, better access to and lower cost of capital, and favourable macro-economic conditions (Debrah et al., 2024). Circular economy is evolving from a marketing operation to a business development strategy that aims, among other things, to extend the product life cycle (Rossi et al., 2022). The general circular economy principles to consider are: maintenance, reuse, remanufacturing and recycling (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2020)(Goswami et al. 2022). With these principles, circular economy enables processes and products to be created that facilitate the repair and further use of components, cooperation

and collaboration with other organisations, finding sustainable solutions through synergies with other companies, using renewable energy and achieving energy efficiency; this refers to reducing energy use, minimising waste or zero waste, generating new specialised job profiles and advancing with the help of science while respecting nature (Gebhardt et al., 2022). Circular economy is a systemic approach to economic development that benefits both business and society (Ellen Macarthur Foundation, 2020), and is one of the most powerful (Gao et al., 2024) and sustainability-oriented movements.

Furthermore, circular economy is closely linked with technological advances through artificial intelligence (AI) tools and the Internet of Things (IoT) from an industry 4.0 (I4.0) perspective that seeks to achieve productivity improvement and value creation by addressing customer needs and operational performance improvements (Awan et al., 2022). This allows the creation of green information systems that improve information flows in organisations, where both hardware and infrastructure are effectively designed towards environmental and social benefits (Kumar & Barua, 2022). In this context, it is important to note that technology is in many organisations a barrier to sustainability due to several factors, mainly economic and adaptability ones (Khurshid et al., 2024).

The literature reviews by, for example, Zavala et al. (2020) identify the need to integrate resilient strategies to manage sustainability and supply chain performance at the strategic, tactical and operational decision levels. Dohale et al. (2021) provides a review on manufacturing strategies about cost leadership, product differentiation, servitisation, international/global manufacturing strategy, and green and sustainable manufacturing strategy from the last 52 years. These authors highlight their evolution to the present day according to I4.0 principles, which support companies in the transition to circular economy by improving the efficiency and sustainability of their supply chain management (Kazancoglu et al., 2023).

According to Amir et al. (2023), a perspective in which the direct and reverse supply chain is properly integrated with the overall objective of achieving circularity in the whole system is lacking. Montag (2023) also states that studies are needed on the theoretical conceptualisation of the circular supply chain, especially on its definition and scope of application. Thus, to our knowledge, no research has addressed the modelling of operations strategies in global supply chains with a sustainable and circular economy criterion. Nor is there evidence for circular economy projects that support the development of relevant policy frameworks and market instruments (Sankaran, 2019). Therefore the demands of globality challenges invite us to articulate strategies for sustainable operations that involve all supply chain actors (i.e., suppliers, producers, distributors, consumers) (Irfan et al., 2022), by further linking advanced digital technologies (Awan et al., 2022), development of green processes and products (Das & Hassan, 2022) and other components that are implicit in the development of strategies such as political, financial, governmental factors. Sustainable supply chain models should address the operations strategies and the barriers that limit their implementation, besides the factors that drive or help the fulfilment of those strategies (Awan et al., 2022), as well as the external and internal factors that affect organisations' performance when engaging with environmental components in their supply chain.

In this context, the need arises to identify and develop new models that lay the foundations for the development, implementation and validation of operations strategies at each supply chain level (Mejia, 2023) because benefits differ depending on each level; for example, emissions and renewable energy use generate a stronger impact from the consumer rather than from the producer (Zhang et al., 2024). This model becomes more relevant because it integrates circular economy principles, which allow to increase financial performance through reuse, cost minimisation, waste reduction, better supplier management and traceability, innovation, reduced emissions, among other benefits (Galdeano-Gómez & García-Fernández, 2024). It is also necessary to find the external factors to the organisation, and its barriers and drivers, and to know which strategies specifically allow for economic, environmental or social benefits. Hence the objective of the present

research is to propose a conceptual model that integrates sustainable operations strategies into global supply chains, which also involves circular economy principles. This will allow researchers, entrepreneurs and all interested parties to learn about environmentally sustainable operations strategies, and all the components and benefits involved in their implementation, to enable them to make strategic decisions, foster global alliances with other companies, analyse customer purchasing behaviour and risks for investment in sustainable and recyclable product design (Holly et al., 2023). All this provides a significant contribution to the theory of industrial engineering, environmental economics and logistics.

The remainder of the article is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the literature review with the selected articles. Section 3 describes the research proposed methodology to design the conceptual model, presents the main concepts of the problem under study and identifies previous conceptual models with their respective design elements, which are adopted as the basis for the proposal. Section 4 provides a conceptual model for linking operations strategies with circular economy principles in sustainable supply chain management. Section 5 discusses and proposes further research and Section 6 concludes.

2. Literature review

This section presents a scientific literature review based on the Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) databases, according to the review methodology proposed by Denyer and Tranfield (2009), which comprises the phases of i) formulating research questions, ii) obtaining relevant literature, iii) selecting and evaluating the literature and iv) analysing and synthesising the selected works. Additionally, the review methodologies proposed by (Gupta et al., 2019) and (Jia et al., 2020) are complementarily considered for the formulation of research questions and the definition of inclusion and exclusion criteria, and for the analysis and synthesis of results, respectively. Thus the following review phases are carried out:

i) Formulating research questions (RQs): (RQ1) what is the current knowledge status of the conceptual models and frameworks that encompass different global supply chain paradigms and sustainability and circular economy concepts?; (RQ2) what are the main structural elements and modelling parameters for a circular and sustainable global supply chain?; (RQ3) what are the research gaps and future research to structure a conceptual model that integrates circular and sustainable operations strategies throughout the supply chain?

ii) Obtaining relevant literature. To answer the RQs, the authors identify the following keywords to search the literature: "operations strategy", "sustainability", "supply chain", "circular economy" and "conceptual model/framework". In this phase, the inclusion criteria consider document type "articles" and the "business, management and accounting", "engineering" and "decision sciences" subject areas in Scopus. The time addressed window goes from 2012 to 2024. For WoS, the considered research areas are "management", "environmental science" and "industrial engineering". Thus the search string in Scopus is defined as follows: ALL ("operations strategy" AND "sustainability" AND "supply chain" AND "circular economy" AND ("conceptual model" OR "conceptual framework")) AND PUBYEAR > 2011 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "BUSI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENGI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")), and the search string in WoS is defined as follows: ALL=(operations strategy AND sustainability AND circular economy AND (conceptual model OR conceptual framework)) AND Article (Document Types) AND (management OR environmental sciences OR industrial engineering (WoS categories)). In addition, the exclusion criteria are related to duplicated publications, and also to proceedings conferences, reviews and articles that do not propose conceptual frameworks.

iii) Selecting and evaluating the literature. The selection process of the search results (Figure 1) by applying the PRISMA methodology (McInnes et al., 2018). Thus after eliminating duplicate articles and filtering them according to the considered exclusion criteria, such as presenting conceptual models or frameworks, addressing operations

strategies, and applying sustainability and circular economy principles, 22 articles were obtained for the analysis.

iv) Analysing and synthesising the selected works.

Table 1 summarises the main contribution, research methodology, operations strategies, circular economy principles and supply chain levels of the selected articles on the conceptual models and frameworks related to operations strategies in sustainable global supply chains according to circular economy principles.

Figure 1. Diagram for the search and selection process of articles.

The research methodologies used in the selected articles are: conceptual, based on literature reviews; descriptive, based on several methods like decision-making trial and evaluation laboratory (Ansari et al., 2022), actor-network theory (Hald & Spring, 2023), principal component analysis, PESTLE-SWOT and interpretive structural modelling (Mishra et al., 2019); empirical and exploratory, based on surveys (Kühl et al. 2020; Jamwal et al. 2021). In addition, four supply chain levels (supplier, producers, distributors and customers) are considered according to the previous works by (Das & Hassan, 2022; Mejia, 2023).

In line with the review methodology, articles are identified based on a conceptual models and frameworks, which describe how to integrate sustainability principles into supply chain management. It is important to note that of the total number of identified papers, 38% address circular economy principles in their operations strategies. It is also noteworthy that these operational strategies are applied at different supply chain levels, but mainly in the manufacturing and customer phases. In this context, only three models apply sustainable operations strategies at all supply chain levels. However, none of them apply circular economy principles at all supply chain levels.

Operations strategies are applied according to their performance objectives at the different supply chain levels. So the supplier level focuses on the acquisition of raw materials in line with green principles, where the selection of suppliers that comply with environmental and social standards, as well as the use of recycled or sustainably sourced materials, are sought to be implemented (Irfan et al., 2022). Another sustainable strategy is to apply extended producer responsibility, which implies that manufacturers must manage the full life cycle of their products, including the recovery, recycling and safe disposal of obsolete products (Kumar et al., 2022).

At the manufacturer level, conceptual models propose adopting cleaner production technologies and efficient processes that reduce energy and water use, and also minimise waste generated during manufacturing (Mishra et al., 2019). Circular product design, circular sourcing, cleaner production and reverse logistics are also proposed as important strategies in line with circular economy principles (Farooque et al., 2022). At the distribution level, the reviewed models propose promoting reverse logistics for the recovery and recycling of products at the end of their useful life and promoting sustainable packaging use (Awan & Sroufe, 2022). In warehousing, implement inventory management

practices that reduce waste and allow the use of energy-efficient facilities are proposed (Das & Hassan, 2022), as is the incorporation of I4.0 technologies to allow the minimisation of transport and the reduction of energy use and CO₂ emissions (Satyro et al., 2023).

Table 1. Summary of reviewed articles.

Author/s	Main contribution	Application context (sector/country)	Research methodology	Operations strategies	Circular economy	Supply chain level			
						Suppliers	Producers	Distributors	Customers
(Ansari et al., 2022)	It provides a framework to evaluate the causal relation between the remanufacturing supply chain and key performance indicators	Bearing manufacturing and remanufacturing industry/India	Descriptive and empirical	Remanufacturing of finished goods and parts				√	
(Awan & Sroufe, 2022)	Identification of key factors for the transition to business models based on circular economy	Construction industry/USA	Empirical	Reuse and recycling of resources			√	√	√
(Birasnav et al., 2022)	It integrates theories for the adoption of green practices in organisations through sustainable supply chain management	Textile industry/China	Conceptual Empirical	Sustainable supply chain management			√	√	√
(Bundgaard & Huulgaard, 2019b)	Creation of a conceptual framework that examines the connections between the fundamental characteristics of luxury products and those of circular economy	Electronics and luxury products industry/Denmark	Conceptual	Finished good repair and extending the product life cycle			√		√
(Cherrafi et al., 2021)	Creation of a self-assessment tool to verify a company's readiness to implement green lean strategies.	Automotive industry	Empirical	Green lean strategies			√		√
(Das & Hassan, 2022)	Identification and analysis of the relation between sustainable supply chain management and organisational performance	Steel, cement and industrial products industry/Bangladesh	Empirical	Sustainable supply chain management			√	√	√
(Davis et al., 2018)	Introduction and enhancement of sustainability activities in service organisations	Fashion industry/Finland	Conceptual	Sustainable services					√
(Farooque et al., 2022)	It enquires about the cost and financial performance to apply circular supply chain management	Education and university research industry/China	Empirical	Circular supply chain management			√		√
(Goswami et al., 2022)	Implementation of collaboration indices at various organisational levels (strategic, tactical and operational)	Construction and mining equipment industry/India	Conceptual Empirical	Sustainable services			√	√	
(Hald & Spring, 2023)	it analyses the implications of the application of the actor-network theory in supply chain management	Not specified	Conceptual	Sustainable supply chain management			√		√
(Irfan et al., 2022)	It explains strategies to achieve production and marketing capabilities through organisational learning and dynamic capabilities in emerging economy suppliers	Not specified	Exploratory	Sustainable suppliers		√			
(Jha et al., 2022)	Identification of the relation between business strategies and supply chain strategies and their impact on supply chain performance and metrics	Manufacturing industry /India	Conceptual Empirical	Enviro-friendly technologies					√
(Kumar et al., 2022)	It promotes the sustainable management of waste electrical and electronic equipment	e-waste management industry/India	Decision theory	Extended producer responsibility					√
(Minaya et al., 2024)	It proposes a DASOBI (drivers, actors, strategies, obstacles, benefits and impact) conceptual framework that benefits manufacturing companies in the transition to digital servitisation	Digital services industry/USA	Conceptual	Digital servitisation					√
(Mishra et al., 2019)	It identifies the most significant factors that drive the effective and efficient management of international manufacturing networks by placing an emphasis on environmental sustainability	International manufacturing networks	Exploratory	Sustainable product manufacturing and eco-efficiency					√
(Pohlmann et al., 2020)	It explores some approaches to achieve sustainable supply chain management: corporate social responsibility, green supply chain management	Poultry supply chain/Brazil	Empirical	Sustainable supply chain management					√
(Rossi et al., 2022)	Development of a conceptual framework to assess the sustainability of the product life cycle extension strategies in industrial contexts	Wood processing machinery manufacturing industry/ Switzerland	Conceptual	Life cycle extension strategies	√		√	√	
(Satyro et al., 2023)	It identifies and analyses the possible cleaner production strategies associated with Industry 4.0	Mechanical industry/Brazil	Conceptual	Cleaner production strategies associated with Industry 4.0			√		

(Shukla & Adil, 2022a)	It proposes a conceptual model of maturity stages for the adoption of green technologies in relation to the decision areas of the manufacturing operations strategy	Paint industry/India	Conceptual Empirical	Adoption of green technologies in relation to manufacturing strategy decision areas		√	√		√
(Zennaro et al., 2022)	It identifies the main areas of logistics research related to the implementation of e-commerce and key performance factors and indicators by paying special attention to sustainable aspects	E-commerce industry/UK	Conceptual	E-commerce according to environmental sustainability principles	√		√	√	√
(Zhao et al., 2017)	Proposal of a multi-objective optimisation model for a green supply chain management scheme	Sanitary products/China	Empirical	Green technology			√	√	
(Zhou et al., 2024)	It presents sustainable servitisation as an alternative to manufacture products and/or services in a more sustainable way throughout their life cycle	Not specified	Conceptual	Sustainable servitisation	√				√

Regarding consumers, models propose training and enabling them to perform products responsible use, and to also encourage recycling and reuse practices (Das & Hassan, 2022). At this level, the aim is to also maximise the value of products and waste in products' life cycle phases (Davis et al., 2018).

Additionally, the identified models allow the identification of remarkable elements in their structures that serve as support to generate new sustainable strategies in the supply chain as inputs and outputs of the model (Farooque et al., 2022), success factors (Jha et al., 2022) and circularity drivers (Mishra et al., 2019). To do so, Awan et al. (2022) focus on the supply chain transition to circular economy by highlighting the interconnection between different key elements that facilitate this transformation, such as collaboration with stakeholders, including external factors like support from governments, businesses and communities, and pricing mechanisms that promote reuse and recycling.

Ansari et al. (2022a) propose evaluating supply chain performance by applying the strategy of remanufacturing products and components through performance indicators, the most prominent of which are: existence of hazardous contamination in the material, end-of-life collection mechanism, commitment to delivery, customer satisfaction level and product disassembly. These indicators can be applied in a sustainable supply chain. However, there is no evidence for an evaluation of the results obtained by applying such a strategy. For sustainable supply chain management, the influence of external institutional pressures, such as government regulations and industry standards, on organisational behaviour towards sustainability must also be considered in addition to internal factors (Birasnav et al., 2022). In a circular economy environment, it is important to evaluate product durability, extended warranties, availability of parts and spare parts, and to assess how these strategies impact consumer perceptions and financial performance (Bundgaard & Huulgaard, 2019b).

Therefore, we conclude that there are no studies based on operations strategies that address circular economy principles along the entire local or global supply chain at both the levels of: suppliers, producers, distributors and customers; generating a research gap between operations strategies and environmental sustainability in global supply chains. Hence the analysed conceptual models address sustainable operations strategies and disclose the strategy used for their execution. However, the inputs, outputs, limitations, external factors and drivers that affect the model could be provided in an integrated way, which would encourage the generation of a novel conceptual model to consider these aspects in global, circular and sustainable supply chains.

3. Research methodology

A conceptual model is an abstract and simplified representation of a system, phenomenon or process designed to facilitate its understanding and analysis (Nguyen et al., 2009). This representation identifies the relevant variables, classifies them, describes their interactions and allows them to be diagrammed (Becerra et al., 2025). Here the methodology by

(Hernández et al., 2008) is adopted as the basis to develop a new conceptual model (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Phases of the methodology followed to develop a conceptual model (adapted from (Hernández et al., 2008a))

In the first phase, we perform a visualisation of the components for the model's structure by a literature review (Section 2) and semistructured interviews (Section 4) with six bus manufacturing companies held with industrial managers.

In the second phase, an analysis of the reviewed literature and the responses obtained from industrial managers by the semistructured interviews held in the first phase is carried out. In this way, the operations strategies in the global supply chains that meet the sustainability principles according to circular economy criteria are identified, as are the input and output parameters (Zennaro et al., 2022), success factors (Jha et al., 2022) and limitations to implement such strategies (Reyes et al., 2021).

In the third phase, the identified parameters are conceptualised and the relations among them are determined to generate a model of integrated theoretical constructs applicable to the proposed problem.

In the fourth phase, a conceptual model called circular and sustainable global supply chain (CS-GSC) as proposed, where the elements described in Phase 2 are considered and analysed in terms of their applicability to all the supply chain levels, the decision areas and the performance objectives of the operations strategies. In addition, the external and internal factors that affect the applicability of operations strategies are identified. The model also adds external favourable factors to the supply chain to help its development and applicability.

In the fifth phase, the model is validated in the metal-mechanical bodywork industrial sector of companies that manufacture and sell buses in Ecuador. Consistently, other conceptual models have been previously validated in specific sectors and countries, such as: the automotive sector in Spain (Hernández et al., 2008a), the footwear sector in Ecuador (Reyes et al., 2021), the automated parking system industry in Norway (Ali et al., 2023) and the cooper mining sector in Chile (Becerra et al., 2025).

Finally in the sixth phase, the obtained results are evaluated and presented for their implementation.

4. Conceptual modelling

Here a reference methodology for conceptual modelling whose main phases are (Hernández et al., 2008b) 1) visualisation, 2) analysis, 3) conceptualisation, 4) modelling, 5) validation and 6) proposal is developed.

4.1 Visualisation

Apart from the inputs obtained from the literature review in Section 2, as a second source of information to develop the conceptual model, and to contribute other elements to its design, information is collected from six companies in the bus manufacturing industry. This productive sector is chosen because its operational manufacturing processes are among those that generate a large amount of solid waste and polluting gas emissions. In production volume terms, the geographical area where the selected companies are located concentrates approximately 65% of the total Ecuadorian bus manufacturing industry (Morales et al., 2018), which makes it an ideal environment to directly observe the sector's production and environmental practices. Here we focus on the bus assembling industry, in which the total number of Ecuadorian bus assemblers comes to 18. We selected six representative bus assembly companies based on their income, number of employees and creation year (SCVS, 2025). They are also among those that generate the most expenditure and investment in environmental management (INEC, 2023). Specifically, the six selected companies are those listed in Table 2 below.

The interview includes questions organised on these dimensions: policies, products-processes, recycling, customers and transport (Das & Hassan, 2022). See the Appendix.

More details of companies, position and years experience of those interviewed can be found in Table 2. The interview includes questions organised on these dimensions: policies, products-processes, recycling, customers and transport (Das & Hassan, 2022). See the Appendix.

Table 2. Company data

Industry	Position	Experience in position (years)	Number of employees	Company size	Creation year	Income (USD/year)	Sustainable costs/investments (USD/year)
Company 1	Chief manager	25	70	medium	1961	3,599,764.00	20,650.00
Company 2	Chief manager	20	64	medium	1969	2,000,785.00	11,700.00
Company 3	Production manager	8	35	small	1978	898,220.00	8,750.00
Company 4	Quality manager	9	25	small	2002	589,936.00	9,780.00
Company 5	Production manager	2	42	small	2003	6,785,897.00	18,840.00
Company 6	Chief manager	15	68	medium	1964	1,757,828.00	18,350.00
Average values in the sector						2,605,405.17	14,678.33

It is important to highlight that holding interviews with the companies under study provided the results summarised in Table 3, which indicates that the characteristics are met by all six evaluated companies. The questions and assessed characteristics on sustainability issues are taken as a reference from the environmental objectives of the structural survey of companies conducted by the National Institute of Statistics and Cense of Ecuador.

Based on the results in Table 3, below is a description of the results collected in companies based on the dimensions proposed in the Appendix. The dimensions considered are: policies, product-processes, recycling and customers.

Table 3. Results of company interviews

Assessed characteristics	Company					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Material waste management	✓	✓		✓		✓
Training in environmental practices	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Environmental standards				✓		
Partnerships with recycling companies					✓	✓
Occupational health and safety	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Supplier qualification	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
External support						
Budget for environmental protection	✓		✓			✓
After-sales service		✓	✓		✓	
Technology and innovation				✓		✓

- Policies. Only one industry applies Environmental Standard ISO 14001:2015 because the rest do not meet the minimum qualification requirements and indicate that they only have quality standards. It is also mentioned that they do not receive support from external governmental bodies, financial institutions or non-governmental organisations (NGOs) for their companies' environmental management.
- Product-processes. Manufacturing processes generate waste materials, especially the fibreglass and metal profiles used for structures, which do not have a reuse plan.
- Recycling. Most of the industries do not have strategic alliances with recycling companies. However, hazardous waste is delivered to waste management companies, while recyclable waste is delivered to environmentally licensed companies. They also mentioned that there is funding for environmental protection, which is considered to form part of budgets as a cost. Companies also pointed out that they train their employees in environmental planning, environmental care, reforestation, waste management and recycling.
- Customers. They stated having effective communication strategies with customers by offering them after-sales services, but in relation to quality and guarantees, because the products generated for buses are not recyclable or remanufacturable.

4.2 Analysis

In terms of the analysed literature reviews, it is indicated that the most relevant drivers for achieving sustainable management in supply chains are: research and development capacities, digitalisation, extended producer responsibility, control of illegal imports and dumping, environmental regulations and policies on recycling, using green or cleaner technologies for recycling (Kumar et al., 2022). Circular economy principles also apply to products, which drive companies to maintain high quality and durability (Bundgaard & Huulgaard, 2019b). Additionally, to achieve a higher degree of sustainability, companies not only need to design their supply chain operations and processes, but must also empower and incentivise their customers to be active participants in sustainable value creation (Davis et al., 2018).

Regarding case studies, in a Brazilian poultry company the operations strategies for compliance with SDGs are analysed, which identify that sustainable supply chain management, corporate social responsibility, industrial ecology, stakeholders theory, circular economy and the science of sustainability are the most relevant (Pohlmann et al., 2020). So for companies to be competitive and sustainable, they must efficiently manage their production planning and control by aligning business strategy with operations strategies, and have to disseminate the strategy within and outside their company (Satyro et al., 2023). In addition, scenarios are proposed to optimise the ecological supply chain management by aiming to minimise risks, carbon emissions and economic costs (Zhao et al., 2017). Product reuse in supply chains is another strategy used to achieve sustainability, where the most relevant drivers are consumer awareness of recycling, technological compatibility between organisations and skilled labour (Ansari et al., 2022). Another key factor for achieving global supply chains is inter-organisational cooperation at different

organisational levels, where the effectiveness of collaboration is measured at the strategic, tactical and operational levels (Goswami et al. 2022).

An empirical study analysed the effect of global supply chain management on cost and financial performance in China. It found that companies belonging to green industrial parks have better sustainability results because compliance with these practices is encouraged and motivated in parks (Farooque et al., 2022). It is worth noting that assessing the effect of sustainable supply chain management, competitive advantage and customer relationship management on organisational performance allows to respond to market demands and to transfer appropriate resources to improve manufacturing processes (Das & Hassan, 2022). In this context, companies need to manage strategic enablers and monitor tactical enablers to achieve sustainability objectives and to support their transition to circular economy (Awan & Sroufe, 2022).

After conducting a principal component analysis, Mishra (2019) determine that the drivers of effective and efficient management of sustainable supply chain management are political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental. Sustainable supply chain management practices, such as circular product design, circular procurement, cleaner production, and product and waste management, allow to maximise environmental and economic benefits (Rossi et al., 2022). In this context, the requirements according to which supply chain performance should be assessed are cost, quality, speed and customer satisfaction (Jha et al., 2022). Finally, the dimensions to be considered for moving towards clean and sustainable production through Industry 4.0 are strategy, waste, recycling, life cycle, resources, energy, production, labour, performance and the environment (Birasnav et al., 2022).

In addition to the elements for a circular and sustainable model of operations strategies in global supply chains based on the literature review the elements that the assessed companies use in their environmentally sustainable environment include: training in environmental practices for both operating and administrative personnel; implementation of occupational health and safety standards, policies, procedures and activities, technical qualification of suppliers, which allows them to obtain good quality materials and inputs, and ensures that these inputs come from companies that practice and apply environmental standards. Other elements that can be added to the model, albeit applied to a lesser extent by companies, are: post-sales service on quality issues, solid waste management with qualified companies, and the implementation of a budget for current spending and investment that allows them to manage and mitigate the environmental impacts caused by their industrial activities.

4.3 Conceptualisation

From the previous literature review (Section 2), it is possible to identify and corroborate the various factors that the authors consider in the proposed conceptual model by taking into account the elements of input, operations strategies with their respective activities, and products and outputs at each supply chain level. It is also necessary to add the factors that achieve success in the proposed activities, constraints and factors external to organisations. This allows companies to align their supply chain, sustainability operations strategies and supply chain principles, assess compliance with requirements and their responsibility for the environment, and verify the constraints and conditions for compliance while considering the supply chain's performance objectives and the decision areas where they are applied.

The proposed conceptual model is made up of the operations strategies and their respective activities, which are aligned to environmental sustainability and circular economy principles. To develop these strategies, criteria linked with the environmental objectives must be entered (Birasnav et al., 2022) and will result in benefits within the environmental, economic and social framework, which we called outputs. In addition, there are drivers in the model for each strategy called success factors (Ansari et al., 2022), as well as the respective constraints that limits all the strategies from being fulfilled and need to be

considered to propose to organisations the mitigation of these constraints and to, thus, achieve sustainability (Cherrafi et al. 2021). Finally, the factors that are external to organisations, but are interdependent to achieve the objectives, are integrated into the model (Mishra et al., 2019).

Inputs are considered factors that are fed into the model and influence the behaviour of operational strategies to make the model sustainable. Thus both the literature review and the company interviews yield seven inputs, which are detailed in Table 4. Similarly, 10 outputs are identified, which are the expected effects or benefits that will be obtained after implementing sustainable and circular strategies in the economic, environmental and social contexts. Table 4 shows the inputs and outputs defined for this conceptual model.

Table 4. Inputs and outputs of the conceptual model

Input number	Inputs	Author/s	Interviewed companies	Output number	Outputs	Author/s	Interviewed companies
1	Enviro-friendly operating processes	(Kumar et al., 2022)		1	Competitiveness	(Birasnav et al., 2022)	✓
2	Environmental concepts in the product life cycle	(Birasnav et al., 2022)		2	Value creation and economic benefits	(Mishra et al., 2019), (Pohlmann et al., 2020)	
3	Green logistics	(Awan & Sroufe, 2022)		3	Efficient internal management	(Zhao et al., 2017)	
4	Storage capacity	(Kumar et al., 2021)	✓	4	Extended product life	(Bundgaard & Huulgaard, 2019b)	✓
5	Ecological management	(Zennaro et al., 2022)	✓	5	Cost minimisation	(Ansari et al., 2022)	
6	Environmental sustainability principles	(Awan et al., 2022)	✓	6	Market price increase	(Davis et al., 2018)	
7	Eco-efficiency activities	(Mishra et al., 2019)		7	Improving organisational performance	(Jha et al., 2022), (Goswami et al., 2022)	✓
				8	Increased resource efficiency	(Shukla & Adil, 2022b), (Mishra et al., 2019)	
				9	Green goods and services	(Awan & Sroufe, 2022), (Irfan et al., 2022)	✓
				10	Minimising carbon emissions	(Mishra et al., 2019)	

Additionally, from the literature review (Section 2) the operations strategies applied in supply chain management are identified and detailed in Table 5. Based on the literature review and company interviews, the activities carried out to obtain and develop these operations strategies are defined.

To identify sustainable operations strategies in the reviewed articles, as a basis we apply the study proposed by Aldás et al. (2023) on theoretical advances in supply chain operations strategies with a circular economy approach, whose main results highlight the strategies for operations based on global supply management, reverse logistics, the implementation of multiple life cycle products, supply chain servitisation, product remanufacturing, I4.0 technologies, circular economy principles and the ReSOLVE (regenerate, share, optimise, loop, virtualise and exchange) model. Considering the aforementioned elements, eight operations strategies are considered (see Table 5).

Table 5. Conceptual model strategies and activities

Operations strategy	Activities	Deduced by author/s	Induced by Interviewed companies
Green shopping	Negotiating with green suppliers	(Birasnav et al., 2022)	
	Procurement of enviro-friendly inputs	(Awan & Sroufe, 2022)	✓
	Application of green logistics in procurement	(Irfan et al., 2022)	
Energy efficiency	Strategic alliances with recycling companies	(Jha et al., 2022)	✓
	Creation of alternative energies	(A. Kumar et al., 2022)	
Green technology	Minimising fossil fuel use		
	Controlling CO ₂		
	Application of big data analytics	(Satyro et al., 2023)	
Green production	Use of artificial intelligence	(Benzidia et al., 2021)	
	Intelligent information systems		
	Managing Industry 4.0 strategies		
Ecological responsibility	Eco-design	(Kumar et al., 2022)	
	Green processes	(Mishra et al., 2019)	
	Green manufacturing	(Satyro et al., 2021)	
	Green products		✓
	Lean manufacturing		✓
Green logistics	Production planning and control		✓
	Staff training in environmental issues	(Zennaro et al., 2022)	
	Customer training in ecological issues		✓
Circular economy principles	Implementing occupational health and safety in recycling activities	(Mishra et al., 2019)	
	Shared services	(Zennaro et al., 2022),	
	Last-mile logistics	(Goswami et al., 2022),	
Green finance	Servitisation	(Zhou et al., 2024),	✓
	Waste minimisation	(Minaya et al., 2024)	
	Product reuse	(Kumar et al., 2022),	
	Reduction	(Ansari et al., 2022),	
	Recycling	(Awan & Sroufe, 2022),	
	Remanufacturing	(Bundgaard & Huulgaard, 2019b),	✓
	Product repair	(Mishra et al., 2019),	✓
Extending the product life cycle	(Pohlmann et al., 2020),		
Green finance	Reverse logistics	(Zennaro et al., 2022),	
	Paying environmental taxes	(Kreye, 2023)	
	Investing in environmental management	(Farooque et al., 2019)	
	Generating current expenses in environmental sustainability activities	(Guo & Liu, 2020)	✓

4.3.1 Operations strategies description

In global supply chains, it is important to incorporate a sustainability dimension by implementing green operations strategies to meet customer needs and to maintain responsibility for environmental protection (A. Kumar et al., 2022).

A positive influence of global supply chain management on a company's environmental performance, measured in terms of improved environmental standards and compliance, as well as reducing harmful emissions, wastewater and solid waste, has been demonstrated (Birasnav et al., 2022). Based on the above, the considered strategies are described below:

To implement supply chain green management practices, it is necessary to start with green shopping, which involves mainly the suppliers that must comply with the environmental care component with their products (Birasnav et al. 2022). For this purpose, environmental audits of suppliers are carried out on an ongoing basis (Liu et al., 2017). During this process, negotiation with green suppliers should be framed in terms of obtaining a low price for recyclable products, green inputs and discounts for green raw materials (Awan & Sroufe, 2022). In this context, with direct information from the interviewed companies, the strategic alliances with recycling companies are also considered because it is important to maintain a good relationship between suppliers and customers by prioritising product development and marketing capabilities because suppliers seek to move up the value chain (Irfan et al., 2022).

Energy efficiency is framed within the generation and use of alternative energies, such as employing solar panels or wind energy to develop production processes and to, thus, minimise fossil fuel use, which will also imply reducing CO₂ emissions (Kumar et al. 2022). Here it is highlighted that, currently, there are already environmental policies that control carbon emissions by creating taxes on the maximum allowable limits, which mainly affect industrial sectors' their supply chains and their operations management (Halat et al., 2023).

This is because manufacturing processes are a major user of natural resources and are responsible for around 38% of global CO₂ emissions (Satyro et al., 2021).

Another strategy to consider is green technologies, where intelligent information systems are applied to optimise organisations in terms of response time, physical space and transport (Benzidia et al., 2021). In this context, technological processes are applied using artificial intelligence according to industry 4.0 implementation principles (Cañas et al., 2021), which encompass several digital technologies, procedures and systems to make the production process more personalised and autonomous so that it can achieve better performance (Awan et al., 2022). Applying artificial intelligence to manufacturing leads to improved processes, real-time responses to different situations, and the optimisation of resources and costs (Benzidia et al., 2021).

Green production is another fundamental strategy because it starts with the eco-design of green products and it plans production in an ecological context, i.e. optimising resources and taking care of the environment (Kumar et al., 2022). The development of green products often involves completely redesigning processes that, in turn, generates costs or investments that industries are not often willing to incur. Lean manufacturing is also used in green production, which integrates principles that seek to eliminate waste in different production process stages and provides a potential solution to help companies to use their resources more efficiently by identifying and eliminating waste (Cherrafi et al., 2021).

Another strategy is ecological responsibility, which is to be shown by suppliers, producers and customers, especially by training them in environmental issues, recycling and environmental sustainability activities (Mishra and Singh, 2022; Zennaro et al., 2022), it is important to note that this strategy is widely used in the companies evaluated for this study. The aim is to reduce waste and to retain as much value as possible from employed products and resources (Pohlmann et al., 2020).

Green logistics consists of methods and procedures to carry out the operations of production, supply, transport and distribution of goods by respecting the environment (Zennaro et al., 2022) *via* a balance between economy and ecology. Its main activities include: reducing transport mileage, minimising emissions from moving goods, last-mile logistics and the intelligent resources use (Goswami et al. 2022). This also applies to servitisation, which is a new business model that seeks to integrate services into a company's offer in a way that maximises customer value while minimising any negative environmental impact and promoting social welfare (Zhou et al., 2024). Servitisation, when combined with technology, facilitates more predictive, personalised and proactive services, drives efficiency and fosters innovation (Minaya et al., 2024). Servitisation is a strategy that is gaining momentum in the industries evaluated in this study by means of after-sales service, such as repairs or refurbishment.

Circular economy is also linked with servitisation, where a framework is proposed that details the necessary relations for the recovery, processing and marketing of circular products, parts or components where servitised circular supply chains are created (Kreye, 2023). A main strategy is related to circular economy principles, which motivates products to achieve durability, repairability, serviceability, extended warranties and after-sales indicators. To develop this strategy, among other activities, reverse logistics is used, where economic, environmental, raw materials and material return strategies must be integrated in an appropriate and articulated way to return to consumers in compliance with warranty offerings (Trollman & Colwill, 2020). Within the reduction framework, the aim is to prolong the useful life of products by preserving capital through redesign. One part of reuse is to refurbish products and exclude waste, and to recycle, which is reusing waste.

Green finance, should promote economic freedom because it is a fundamental factor that must be considered above all else, and not only in manufacturing, but also in any transnational process (Mishra et al., 2019).

4.3.2 Operations strategies evaluation

The conceptual model proposes applying operations strategies in sustainable supply chain management. Therefore, each one is evaluated according to the performance objectives and decision areas proposed by Slack and Lewis (2023). The following are considered among the performance objectives: quality, which is the level of specification of a product or service. With it, whether the product/service is fit for the purpose for which it was created is analysed; speed, which is the time from when customers place their order until it is received; flexibility, which is the ability to adapt to changes and disruptions; cost, where it is important to highlight that companies will always seek to minimise their production costs to be more competitive; resilience, which is the ability to recover from adverse, fortuitous and unforeseen situations (Slack & Lewis, 2023). Decision areas correspond to the actions to be taken by operations managers in relation to: capacity, which is the volume of production achieved with existing resources; process technology, which are decisions about equipment, machinery and the information technologies involved in the supply chain; the supply network, which represents the structure formed among suppliers, producers, distribution and customers; development and organisation, which, on the one hand, comprise the improvement of processes and products in both the long and short terms and, on the other hand, refer to the way in which resources are grouped: tangibility, functionality, characteristics and markets (Aragón and MacDonell, 2009).

Table 6 shows the results of evaluating the fulfilment of the performance objectives and the decision areas present in each proposed operations strategy. It can be seen that all the operations strategies are present in the capacity area, which means that a global sustainable supply chain allows customer satisfaction by achieving the production volume using all the existing resources for this purpose. In this context, it is worth considering the application of technology because not all strategies implement process and information technologies into their implementation, except for green technology, green production and circular economy. This analysis also shows that some strategies do not integrate the entire supply chain and apply their objectives only at one supply chain level. Finally, it is noted that organisation and development are present in all the strategies because each one focuses on process improvement and the correct grouping of resources.

Regarding performance objectives, Table 6 shows that, except for green finance, operations strategies are quality-oriented, possibly because of not being linked with costs and investment. Green technology and green production are the only ones whose objectives involve speed, while circular economy, green finance and green production are oriented mainly to achieve cost minimisation. Finally, it is noted that most strategies are flexible, adaptable and resilient, except for green finance.

Table 6. Operations strategies evaluation

Decision areas	Operations strategies							
	Green shopping	Energy efficiency	Green technology	Green production	Ecological responsibility	Green logistics	Circular economy	Green finance
Capacity	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Technology		✓	✓				✓	
Supply network	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
Development and organisation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Performance objectives								
Quality	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Speed			✓	✓				
Flexibility	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Cost				✓			✓	✓
Resilience	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	

4.3.3 Successful factors

For the conceptual model, success factors are defined as those elements that drive and support the achievement of operations strategies, namely: teamwork, which promotes continuous improvement and effective communication to fulfil the environmental

objectives in the organisation (Cherrafi et al., 2021); continuous training and education for both managers and employees in circular economy, sustainability and environmental management issues by promoting an enviro-friendly production environment, and to also allow to obtain qualified personnel in the area (Birasnav et al., 2022); cooperation with suppliers, where strategic information exchange is achieved to address volatile demand scenarios (Jha et al., 2022); reward mechanisms with customers, which is based on creating efficient recycling networks, affordable prices of reused/guaranteed products and marketability (Ansari et al., 2022); finally, performance measurement is highlighted as a success factor because it is important to assess compliance with environmental targets with suppliers, producers and transport to be successful across the whole supply chain (Birasnav et al. 2022).

4.3.4 Limitations

The following constraints to achieve operations strategies are highlighted: governments not ensuring sustainable management and efficient natural resources use (Pohlmann et al., 2020); lack of technology to develop sustainability strategies that enable the implementation of circular economy, such as reuse, green product design and smart information systems (Saha et al., 2021); lack of sustainability awareness; this factor must be fulfilled both internally and externally to organisations to set up efficient sustainable resource management with both producers and consumers (Cherrafi et al., 2021); lack of knowledge of not only the key dimensions of global supply chain management practices, but also of the influencing factors and benefits achieved by applying such practices (Birasnav et al., 2022); companies' uncertainty when estimating the real impact that adopting circular economy strategies can have on their activities from environmental and economic perspectives, and their fear of failure when applying them (Rossi et al., 2022); financial constraints, which are a component that hinders activities involving waste reduction, industry 4.0 application, technology implementation and alternative energy management being performed (Cherrafi et al. 2021).

4.3.5 Factors external to organisations

The literature review also identifies the external factors that drive the development of sustainable supply chains, such as support from financial institutions, NGOs support, national, regional and local governments, universities and civil society movements (Marcon et al., 2023). In this context, the stability of governments plays an important role in the sustainable growth of the supply chain (Mishra et al., 2019), and allows for a permanent connection with other social actors (Fuentes et al., 2024). So also having agents/organisations that fund sustainability initiatives is necessary because many of them involve high costs that companies cannot self-fund (Farooque et al. 2019). Some external factors have been considered in the PESTLE strategic analysis tool, such as: political, legal, environmental, social and economic factors, since when proposing strategies in global chains, these external factors directly affect the achievement of the strategies of operations within the framework of environmental sustainability (Phan, 2021).

4.4 Modelling

The model is proposed by integrating all the identified operations strategies and placing them at each supply chain level (suppliers, producers, distributors, customers), which are integrated according to circular economy principles (take, make, distribution, use, reuse) (Mishra et al., 2019). They are also analysed in terms of sustainability principles (economic, social, environmental) and include another principle: the technological principle (Zhao et al., 2017).

The proposed model integrates the operations strategies identified in the literature review and company surveys, which are aligned to the supply chain levels. For each operations strategy, several activities are described in Table 5, which are classified

according to the sustainability dimensions. To develop strategies, there are components associated with operations strategies, which are referred to as inputs, and the results expected from the applying the model, which are referred to as outputs. The model also presents the success factors that drive the implementation of strategies, as well as the constraints or barriers that might hinder the development of strategies. In addition, the external factors that favour fulfilling the objectives outlined in each strategy are considered. It is important to note that operations strategies are evaluated in terms of performance objectives and decision areas. Figure 3 is a graphical representation of the conceptual model, which starts from the centre with the four supply chain links and associates them with circular economy principles and then links all these elements with the strategies for sustainable operations and success factors.

As the proposed conceptual model has circular economy principles and the links of the supply chain at its core, all this could guarantee its generic applicability in different contexts. However, specific operations strategies from determined regions and sectors could be also contemplated to foster their suitability to governmental and political implications depending on, for instance, countries because each one determines its policies, environmental requirements, green taxes and financial incentives. It is for this reason that the model considers these external factors to validate its adaptability or scalability.

Note: **Inputs:** 1: Enviro-friendly operating processes, 2: Environmental concepts in the product life cycle, 3: Green logistics, 4: Storage capacity, 5: Ecological management, 6: Environmental sustainability principles, 7: Eco-efficiency activities. **Outputs:** 1: Competitiveness, 2: Value creation and economic benefits, 3: Efficient internal management, 4: Extended product life, 5: Cost minimisation, 6: Market price increase, 7: Improving organisational performance, 8: Increased resource efficiency, 9: Green goods and services, 10: Minimising carbon emissions.

Figure 3. Conceptual CS-GSC model.

4.5 Model verification and validation

In this phase, the first step is to verify compliance with the operations strategies, inputs, outputs and success factors in each company. Subsequently, a validation of the model's structure is carried out to verify the usefulness of each element and its articulation with the operations strategies to achieve sustainability and circularity in this industrial manufacturing sector. Validation is performed in six industrial small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). These companies receive the chassis onto which they assemble the metal bus structure. The final product is the body to be ready to serve urban and interprovincial public transport.

Production processes generate waste, such as metal parts of the structure, glass fibre residue, glue residue, paint, upholstery fabric, the paper used for the painting process, metal and wood shavings, oils, solvents and wastewater.

To evaluate the conceptual model, a semistructured survey was developed by identifying compliance with inputs, outputs, operations strategies, constraints and success factors. In this way, the production managers of each company were questioned *in situ* (Table 7). This methodology enabled diagnosing the possibility of applying the conceptual proposal to improve sustainable supply chain processes based on circular economy principles (Reyes et al., 2021).

Table 7. Verification and validation of the conceptual model

Model Elements	Company					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Inputs	Enviro-friendly operating processes	Enviro-friendly operating processes	Enviro-friendly operating processes	Enviro-friendly operating processes	Enviro-friendly operating processes	Enviro-friendly operating processes
	Environmental concepts in the product life cycle	Environmental concepts in the product life cycle				Environmental concepts in the product life cycle
	Storage capacity			Green logistics		
	Ecological management	Ecological management	Ecological management	Ecological management	Storage capacity	Ecological management
	Environmental sustainability principles	Environmental sustainability principles		Environmental sustainability principles	Environmental sustainability principles	Environmental sustainability principles
	Eco-efficiency activities	Eco-efficiency activities		Eco-efficiency activities		
Operations strategies	Green shopping	Green shopping	Green shopping	Green shopping		Green shopping
					Energy efficiency	Energy efficiency
				Green technology		Green technology
	Green production	Green production		Green production		Green production
	Ecological responsibility	Ecological responsibility	Ecological responsibility	Ecological responsibility	Ecological responsibility	Ecological responsibility
	Green logistics				Green logistics	
Outputs	Circular economy principles	Circular economy principles		Circular economy principles		Circular economy principles
	Green finance		Green finance			Green finance
	Competitiveness	Competitiveness	Competitiveness	Competitiveness	Competitiveness	Competitiveness
	Value creation and economic benefits	Value creation and economic benefits	Value creation and economic benefits	Value creation and economic benefits	Value creation and economic benefits	Value creation and economic benefits
	Efficient internal management		Efficient internal management		Efficient internal management	
	Cost minimisation	Cost minimisation	Cost minimisation	Cost minimisation	Cost minimisation	Cost minimisation
Limitations	Market price increase	Market price increase	Market price increase	Market price increase	Market price increase	Market price increase
	Improving organisational performance	Improving organisational performance	Improving organisational performance	Improving organisational performance	Improving organisational performance	Improving organisational performance
	Increased resource efficiency		Increased resource efficiency	Increased resource efficiency		Increased resource efficiency
	Green goods and services	Green goods and services		Green goods and services		Green goods and services
	Minimising carbon emissions			Minimising carbon emissions		Minimising carbon emissions
	Governments not ensuring sustainable management	Governments not ensuring sustainable management	Governments not ensuring sustainable management	Governments not ensuring sustainable management	Governments not ensuring sustainable management	Governments not ensuring sustainable management
Success factors	Lack of knowledge of the key dimensions				Lack of sustainability awareness	Lack of knowledge of the key dimensions
	Companies' uncertainty	Companies' uncertainty	Companies' uncertainty	Companies' uncertainty	Companies' uncertainty	Companies' uncertainty
	Financial constraints	Financial constraints	Financial constraints	Financial constraints	Financial constraints	Financial constraints
	Teamwork	Teamwork	Teamwork	Teamwork	Teamwork	Teamwork
	Continuous training and education					
	Qualified personnel	Qualified personnel	Qualified personnel	Qualified personnel	Qualified personnel	Qualified personnel
	Cooperation with suppliers	Cooperation with suppliers		Cooperation with suppliers		
	Reward mechanisms					Reward mechanisms
				Performance measurement	Performance measurement	

With regard to model inputs, enviro-friendly operating processes and ecological management are applied in all the companies due to requirements of environmental

regulations (Zennaro et al., 2022) and, thus, allow to promote sustainable development, reduced environmental impacts and increased resource efficiency, and to minimise the CO₂ emissions caused by industrial operations as a way out of the model. Small companies do not consider environmental concepts in their processes in the product life cycle (Birasnav et al., 2022) due to its high implementation costs, but medium-sized companies apply it throughout the supply chain by extending the product's life cycle. One of the least applied inputs is green logistics, which involves transportation, storage capacity, packaging and distribution (Awan & Sroufe, 2022) and, thus, achieves the minimisation of emissions, efficient resources management and increased performance. However, this input is less used due to its high implementation costs according to the answers given by the interviewed entrepreneurs. There are companies that do not apply eco-efficiency, which allows the efficient use of resources like water, energy and materials, in their operations (Mishra et al., 2019) by, thus, minimising costs and increasing resource efficiency as outputs. This input is applied mainly in medium-sized companies because they have personnel and departments dedicated to control these resources. Environmental sustainability principles facilitate organisations and personnel to act with ecological responsibility by promoting rational resources use and preventing impacts Awan et al. (2022). From the model's validation, it can be deduced that the CS-GSC model inputs are linked with the efficient use and ecological management of resources, and the inputs that companies will have the most difficulty in adapting to their operations strategy are storage capacity and green logistics, which involve making more efforts, especially small companies, to adapt eco-efficiency and environmental principles in their product's life cycle. The model shows that most companies are interested in achieving the benefits of circular and sustainable operation strategies, mainly those that allow them to be competitive, create value and economic benefits, minimise costs, increase market prices and improve organisational performance (Figure 4). Given the nature of its products (urban and interprovincial buses manufacturing), this sector finds it more difficult to achieve all this with the model and propose an extension of the useful product life and the minimisation of carbon emissions and sees it with a medium level of difficulty to obtain ecological goods and to efficiently increase resources. Therefore, if it wishes to apply circularity throughout the supply chain, it will have to increase efforts in planning and investing in its environmental management in the supply chain (Shukla & Adil, 2022b).

Companies in this sector see the application of strategies linked with green shopping through organic suppliers as more accessible (Awan & Sroufe, 2022) because, in their operational strategy, they verify that materials and materials come from ecologically responsive companies. This allows them to obtain quality products with recycling or reuse characteristics. Another widely used and easily implemented strategy according to companies is ecological responsibility, which is manifested by permanent personnel training and the implementation of a safety, hygiene and environment department. This strategy is easy to apply especially in the manufacturing phase of the supply chain. In this context, and according to companies' responses, the most difficult strategies to apply are green technology, which allows the minimisation of pollutants through the generation of alternative energies, computerised environmental management systems, process monitoring equipment, and emission control equipment, which are costly and difficult to implement in their field. The strategies that are moderately applied in the evaluated companies are those linked with circular economy principles, mainly in relation to the storage, recycling and reuse of solid waste from manufacturing. Another strategy that they scarcely apply is green logistics, which is linked with the transportation, storage and distribution of products, because bus manufacturing involves only a minority of distribution or storage activities. Besides, green financing has boomed in recent times through organisations that motivate green strategies through financial products with lower costs for companies. (Guo & Liu, 2020) . This strategy allows companies to access economic

resources that will be used partly for the environmental management of their operations and to implement other environmental benefits in the field, such as technology. With the design of green products and processes (Kumar et al., 2022), green production is a strategy that most companies apply. It is done in this sector through lean manufacturing and production planning and control. In summary, the CS-GSC conceptual model facilitates companies in this industrial sector with implementing circular and sustainable operations strategies throughout the supply chain and provides implementation requirements through inputs and the results to be obtained through outputs. The most widely used strategies are green responsibility, green production, green shopping and green production, and the most difficult to implement are green technologies and green logistics; see Figure 5.

The driving factors most widely applied by companies are teamwork and qualified personnel, and those with the least impact are reward mechanisms and performance measurement, because reward mechanisms often involve investing economic resources and hiring qualified personnel to measure operational performance.

The most frequently found limitations in the model that companies believe have the strongest impact are financial limitations because most strategies involve investing economic resources in environmental management activities. Another limitation with a major impact is the uncertainty that is often caused by political and governmental decisions at national and international levels; see Figure 6.

Finally, the conceptual model design addresses the external factors that can drive the implementation of operational strategies, such as government decisions, support from international organisations and financial products that encourage green production practices. Figures 4, 5 and 6 summarise in percentage terms the level of compliance with the verification of the CS-GSC conceptual model elements in the industrial companies under study.

Figure 4. The results of inputs and outputs

Figure 5. Operations strategies results

Figure 6. Limitations and success factors

5. Discussion

Regarding the current knowledge status on the conceptual models and frameworks that encompass different global supply chain paradigms and sustainability and circular economy concepts, a conceptual model that integrates operations strategies across supply chain provides a deeper understanding of implementing sustainability strategies into manufacturing companies, and of the challenges that may arise while being implemented; i.e. the political, managerial, behavioural and technical barriers associated with their execution (Cherrafi et al., 2021). The stakeholders involved in supply chains, including suppliers, producers and customers, must be committed to sustainability and environmental responsibility. Overall, the monitoring and control of activities are important for fulfilling objectives, and for encouraging stakeholder-oriented policies about the environmental and economic benefits of purchasing remanufactured products and

motivating consumers to return used products to collection centres in circular economy environments (Ansari et al., 2022). The review of conceptual models further identifies which factors are critical for maintaining good merchandising and which needs are to be integrated into production processes (Irfan et al., 2022). Most conceptual models involve sustainable operations strategies, but only a few are based on circular economy principles, especially at the supplier stage. This leaves a large gap to be investigated because it is important that sustainability and circularity are embedded throughout the supply chain. Additionally, a supply chain must be socially responsive by being sensitive to its employees and customers' needs (Jha et al., 2022). Sustainable production should ensure eco-efficiency, green design and manufacturing and clean procurement to develop a new logistics system to efficiently use resources by promoting the remanufacturing, recycling and reuse of resources, while minimising carbon emissions in operational processes. However, these ideas of sustainability are limited by several factors to the company, such as national and international government policies external and economic resources for environmental management, especially in emerging economies (Dhillon et al., 2023), as in the case study applied in the model's validation, which opens up future study about the validation of the conceptual model in companies from countries with more developed economies. Environmental sustainability can be taken as a driver of innovation and, in return, innovation promotes accelerated growth in production (Guinot et al., 2022). Circular economy is seen as a systemic approach to economic development, which is designed to benefit business, society and the environment. Therefore, it is important to highlight that both recycling and remanufacturing will not be sufficiently effective without an adequate logistics system, which allows the optimisation of not only the recovery of discarded materials and products and their return to the production system, but also their link with traditional production models (Ansari et al., 2022). Circular economy principles allow the reconditioning of product components for repair, replacing parts, performing dismantling tests and excluding hazardous components in their manufacture. However, these principles are conditioned by future sustainability studies to confirm that if a product lasts longer, fewer products need to be produced (Bundgaard & Huulgaard, 2019b), which affects economic outcomes. Hence for industries to be sustainable, they need to invest in their entire supply chain, new processes, technologies, suppliers and R&D (Satyro et al. 2021).

Therefore, operations strategies management in the production and manufacturing phase must promote intelligent agile manufacturing using technologies that reduce waste, minimise CO₂ emissions and maximise the efficiency of energy resources by seeking sustainable business performance with economic, environmental and social benefits. Green logistics involves minimising energy resources for transporting goods and services, in which context managers must manage the efficient distribution of goods through green storage and transport, and with the effective control of loading and unloading. Training is essential at all organisational levels because the same environmental objective must be maintained in relation to managers, workers, suppliers and consumers. So consumers must perform activities that support circular economy through reuse, storage and proper recycling. With an efficient supply chain, responsible and sustainable consumption and production objectives will be fulfilled by generating products that return to the supply chain and help to maintain an environmental balance.

Regarding model validation, the evaluated companies have difficulties in applying green logistics and efficient storage. They also need to be more efficient in terms of reducing emissions and improving their internal administrative management. As for operations strategies, especially those that focus on circular economy, industries are preferably applying waste minimisation, recycling and product repair, whereas those that should be promoted are product life cycle extension, reverse logistics, product reduction and reuse. It is worth mentioning that the activities which focus on circular economy are present in all the decision areas of the operations strategy and meet performance objectives, except for speed. In the proposed model, circular economy principles focus mainly on customers and transport through waste reduction, reuse and green transport.

6. Conclusions

The main objective of this study is to develop a conceptual model, for a circular and sustainable-global supply chain, to integrate sustainable operations strategies into global supply chains, which involves circular economy principles. To do so, different operations strategies, inputs, outputs, limitations and success factors are identified from various conceptual frameworks through a literature review and a semistructured survey of the companies that integrate sustainability and circular economy into supply chain management. In terms of structural elements and the main modelling parameters for circular and sustainable global supply chains, the identified operations strategies are linked according to environmental care principles, such as green procurement, energy efficiency, green technology, green production, green responsibility, green logistics, application of circular economy principles and green finance. To comply with these operations strategies, it is important to generate enviro-friendly operational processes and apply green management, and to develop not only activities based on eco-efficiency, but also transport models linked by green logistics. To achieve the goals to be reached, companies must: (i) encourage teamwork, continuous training and the acquisition of qualified personnel; (ii) generate reward mechanisms with customers and suppliers; (iii) continuously evaluate performance. However, there will always be constraints that need to be overcome to reach supply chain sustainability goals, such as limited support from government bodies, expensive process technology, lack of environmental awareness at all the supply chain levels, uncertainty, unforeseen and unexpected disruptions like COVID-19 or military conflicts, and fear of failure. Last but not least, companies should seek external support through funding for environmental projects from financial institutions, NGOs and regional governments.

The conceptual CS-GSC model allows to identify the scope and requirements needed to apply operations strategies in supply chains management, and to assess compliance with them in different industrial sectors, because it integrates all the supply chain levels and manifests their operations strategies in terms of sustainability dimensions, decision areas and performance targets.

Theoretical implications from conceptual modelling are related to inform about necessary requirements and assess fulfilling the activities that need to be applied in each operations strategy to achieve a sustainable supply chain. The conceptual model also suggests building on the success factors that are verified in other models and considers constraints that may cause disruptions when managing and implementing operations strategies. Managerial implications are oriented to identify operations strategies, where they are intended to intervene at every supply chain level. So managers must initiate and develop relationships with suppliers with an environmental care philosophy in all their operations to allow them to manage supply chains by obtaining green raw materials, inputs and services. At the global level, supply chains should be managed by national and international relationships with companies that supply products according to the sustainability and circularity philosophy. At a more detailed level, policy implications are directed to the use of the proposed model and validation methodology in companies to identify the status of inputs, operations strategies, outputs, limitations and success factors (Table 7) to improve sustainable supply chain processes based on circular economy principles.

The CS-GSC conceptual model aims to solve the need of those companies that wish to incorporate sustainable operations strategies into their supply chain according to a circular economy approach. To know the minimum requirements, expected results, limitations and factors that drive the benefit of each strategy, the model integrates strategies at all the supply chain levels and proposes strategies for each one. With all this, companies will be able to achieve the enviro-friendly processes currently required to comply with national and international legislation. It will allow them to improve their competitive strategy, align with climate commitments, and circular economy strategies will also permit them to

increase their return on investment through reuse, remanufacturing and waste minimisation. The component that makes this model different is that strategies are applied throughout the supply chain and, at the same time, the elements that facilitate or limit their implementation are integrated.

The limitations of the study are mainly: (i) only a few competing models appear that comprehensively integrate sustainability and circularity concepts into supply chains; (ii) there are very few quantitative studies that allow the economic aspects of the found competing models to be evaluated; (iii) very few or no quantitative works permit the integration of operations strategies into a sustainable supply chain according to circular economy principles; (iv) for the literature review, we used the Scopus and Web of science databases, where it should be noted that the number of found articles can be extended because these databases are constantly being updated and offer new research works every day; (v) the application and validation of the conceptual model to a specific industrial sector in a country could limit the generalisability and applicability of the proposed model to other contexts or industries.

After model verification and validation, the conceptual proposal shows that the least used strategies are energy efficiency, green logistics and green technology. This scenario leaves open a future study that can analyse the operational implications that justify this behaviour. Regarding the model's outputs, the least used variable in the evaluated sector is extended product life, which should be strengthened for being closely linked with circular economy principles and allows, according to the studies carried out, environmental objectives to be fulfilled. Yet it is not being applied. The most outstanding limitations are scarce awareness of sustainability and lack of technology, which leave open another future study in which the factors that affect this behaviour of companies and the elements that influence it (i.e., political, legislative, governmental, environmental) could be investigated. The conceptual model proposes to evaluate external factors like government policies, support from non-governmental organisations and support from financial organisations through incentives for environmental practices in operations strategies. Nevertheless, the studied documents do not detail how these factors benefit or affect the development of operations strategies, and this leaves open another future study to resolve this question.

With respect to the research methodology, further research is proposed to integrate other specific elements into the model by considering different industrial sectors and countries that will allow new results to be acquired from the conceptual model aligned to: (i) validate and apply the conceptual model in different industrial sectors and countries; (ii) propose new conceptual models by also integrating other sectors and economic activities apart from manufacturing; (iii) develop quantitative models and empirical studies that evaluate the application of circular and/or sustainable operations strategies.

Finally, within a global and sustainable supply chain, we encourage future work oriented to quantitative models to be validated in a real-world case study to know all the implications, advantages, disadvantages and economic, environmental and social benefits to be achieved by applying the operations strategies established in this conceptual model.

Data availability statement

The authors confirm that all the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article and the Appendix submitted as a Supplementary Information file.

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Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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